

Optimization of Distinct Time-Series Neural Architectures for Cloud-Edge Workload Prediction

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Abstract—Optimizing resource utilization in cloud-edge networks requires accurate workload prediction under strict computational constraints. Traditional methods like Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) struggle to balance accuracy and efficiency in these dynamic environments. In this paper, we evaluate distinct state-of-the-art time-series architectures for containerized workload prediction, including Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), temporal Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Transformers, and sparse Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs). Through empirical analysis using Bayesian optimization, we identify optimal model configurations for cloud-edge workload prediction. Notably, the MLP model achieves comparable memory prediction accuracy to the best CNN model, while using approximately $7,000\times$ less parameters (i.e., 35 vs. 247,091) and $5\times$ faster inference ($1.84\mu\text{s}$ vs. $7.15\mu\text{s}$). Our findings provide concrete guidance for model selection across different cloud-edge deployment scenarios, from resource-constrained edge devices to high-capacity cloud servers.

Index Terms—cloud-edge computing, workload prediction, time-series forecasting, machine learning, resource management.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rapid advancement of edge computing and cloud-native architectures has transformed the computational landscape, enabling applications to deliver low-latency services by bringing resources closer to end-users. However, this paradigm shift introduces significant challenges in optimizing resource utilization due to highly dynamic and fluctuating workloads inherent in cloud-edge environments. Efficient resource management is critical to meet Quality of Service (QoS) requirements while minimizing operational costs [1].

Accurate workload prediction has emerged as a solution for proactive orchestration and resource management. By forecasting future resource demands, cloud orchestrators can allocate resources more effectively, reducing under-utilization and preventing service degradation [2]. However, precise workload prediction remains complex due to demand fluctuations, workload migrations, and the heterogeneity of cloud-edge environments. This complexity is even stronger at the container level, especially with the rise of microservice architectures that require granular, container-specific elasticity operations. Traditional

prediction models often struggle to capture the complex dynamics of containerized workloads, leading to errors between predicted and actual resource utilization.

The current state-of-the-art in **cloud workload prediction** predominantly relies on Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), particularly Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [2]. While RNNs are effective in modeling temporal dependencies, they have limitations in capturing long-range dependencies and adapting to rapid workload changes common in microservice architectures. Moreover, RNN-based models may not scale efficiently with the increasing complexity and volume of cloud-edge workloads.

Recent advancements in **machine learning literature** have introduced distinct novel architectures that show promise for improving workload prediction accuracy and efficiency. These include Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) [3], Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [4], Transformer models with attention mechanisms [5], and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) techniques [6], [7]. While these models have demonstrated superior performance in capturing complex temporal and spatial patterns in various domains, their potential for cloud-edge workload prediction has yet to be fully realized. Moreover, each of these architectures may require careful adaptation to effectively handle the unique heterogeneous characteristics of containerized workloads in cloud-native environments [8]. Therefore, a systematic comparison and optimization of these advanced architectures are crucial for identifying and tailoring models that can best capture containerized workload patterns while meeting the strict latency and resource constraints of cloud-native environments. This approach will enable more informed model selection and customization for different deployment scenarios.

In this paper, we aim to advance container-level workload prediction in cloud-edge environments by leveraging these state-of-the-art time-series forecasting models. Our key contributions are:

- 1) **Optimized Model Architectures:** We propose a systematic Bayesian optimization framework that automatically tunes advanced time-series architectures (GNNs, CNNs, Transformers, MLPs) for cloud workload prediction, enabling efficient discovery of

optimal model configurations while minimizing computational overhead.

- 2) **Empirical Evaluation:** We conduct an extensive comparative analysis of these models, evaluating their prediction accuracy, computational efficiency, convergence speed, and resource utilization on real-world cloud-edge workload datasets. Our findings provide actionable insights for model selection in diverse cloud-edge scenarios.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the system model and formalizes the workload prediction problem. Section III details the advanced forecasting models and their adaptation to cloud-edge environments. Section IV describes the experimental setup and discusses the results of our comparative analysis. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines potential directions for future research.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We formalize our cloud workload prediction framework in three key components: workload representation, prediction model, and objective function. This formalization provides the mathematical foundation for comparing different architectural approaches.

A. Workload Representation

Let $\mathbf{w}_t = [w_t^{(1)}, w_t^{(2)}, \dots, w_t^{(f)}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^f$ represent the workload vector at discrete time step t , where $w_t^{(i)}$ denotes the i -th resource utilization feature (e.g., CPU, memory usage), f is the number of features, and $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}$, with T being the total number of time steps in the trace. The complete workload trace forms a multivariate time series:

$$\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \dots, \mathbf{w}_T]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times f}. \quad (1)$$

B. Workload Prediction Model

Our objective is to forecast future workload vectors based on historical observations. We define a prediction function $\Psi_\phi : \mathbb{R}^{\kappa \times f} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times f}$, parameterized by $\phi \in \mathbb{R}^p$ which represents the trainable parameters of the prediction model (e.g., weights and biases of a neural network), to estimate the workload over a prediction horizon of length λ , where $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\lambda \geq 1$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda} = \Psi_\phi(\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}), \quad (2)$$

where $\kappa \in \mathbb{N}$, $\kappa \geq 1$, is the length of the historical context window, and $\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t} \in \mathbb{R}^{\kappa \times f}$ denotes the sequence of past workload vectors used for prediction. The model architecture and training process are determined by hyperparameters $\theta \in \Theta$, where Θ defines the search space of valid configurations.

C. Objective Function

To learn the model parameters ϕ , we minimize a loss function that measures the prediction error between the forecasted workload $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda}$ and the ground truth workload $\mathbf{w}_{t+1:t+\lambda}$ across all resource dimensions. We employ the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as our optimization objective, which penalizes larger prediction errors quadratically:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} \|\mathbf{w}_{t+i} - \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+i}\|_2^2, \quad (3)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the Euclidean norm in \mathbb{R}^f and $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, T - \lambda\}$. This loss function computes the average squared distance between predicted and actual resource utilization vectors across the prediction horizon λ .

III. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ADVANCED TIME-SERIES MODELS

We analyze four modern architectures that implement the prediction function Ψ_ϕ from Section II, each targeting specific workload characteristics: Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) model temporal dependencies through graph edges, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) capture local usage patterns, Transformers identify long-range dependencies via self-attention, and Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) offer computationally efficient direct mapping of features to predictions.

A. Graph Neural Network Approaches

GNNs implement the prediction function Ψ_ϕ by modeling temporal data as graph structures [3]. Given the input sequence $\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}$, we construct a graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ with nodes $\mathcal{V} = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_\kappa\}$ representing time steps, and edges \mathcal{E} capturing temporal dependencies. Each node v_i corresponds to the workload vector $\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+i} \in \mathbb{R}^f$.

The parameters $\phi = \{W, U, \mathbf{b}, \theta_{\text{out}}\}$ consist of message passing weights $W, U \in \mathbb{R}^{d_h \times d_h}$, bias $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_h}$, and readout parameters θ_{out} . The hidden state $\mathbf{h}_i^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_h}$ at layer l for node i is computed through iterative updates:

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(0)} = \mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+i} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_i^{(l)} = \sigma \left(W \mathbf{h}_i^{(l-1)} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} U \mathbf{h}_j^{(l-1)} + \mathbf{b} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(i)$ is the neighborhood of node i , and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is an activation function. After L layers of updates, the prediction $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda}$ is generated by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda} = f_{\text{out}} \left(\mathbf{h}_\kappa^{(L)}; \theta_{\text{out}} \right), \quad (6)$$

where $f_{\text{out}} : \mathbb{R}^{d_h} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times f}$ maps the final node embedding to the λ -step prediction, completing the implementation of Ψ_ϕ .

B. Convolutional Neural Network-based Models

CNNs implement the prediction function Ψ_ϕ by capturing local temporal patterns through convolution operations [4]. Given the input sequence $\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}$, the prediction is computed through a series of 1D convolutions along the temporal dimension:

$$\mathbf{X}^{(l)} = \sigma \left(\text{Conv1D} \left(\mathbf{X}^{(l-1)}, \mathbf{F}^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}^{(l)}, d^{(l)} \right) \right), \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^{(0)} = \mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}$, Conv1D denotes the one-dimensional convolution operation with kernel size $K^{(l)}$, $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$ indexes the network layers, $f^{(l)} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the number of channels in layer l with $f^{(0)} = f$, and $d^{(l)} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the dilation factor. The activation function $\sigma(\cdot)$ introduces non-linearity.

The parameters $\phi = \{\{\mathbf{F}^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}^{(l)}\}_{l=1}^L, \theta_{\text{out}}\}$ consist of convolution filters $\mathbf{F}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{K^{(l)} \times f^{(l-1)} \times f^{(l)}}$ and biases $\mathbf{b}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{f^{(l)}}$ for each layer, and readout parameters θ_{out} which transform the final convolutional features into predictions through weight matrices and bias vectors. After L convolutional layers, the prediction $\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda}$ is generated by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda} = f_{\text{out}} \left(\mathbf{X}_t^{(L)}; \theta_{\text{out}} \right), \quad (8)$$

where $f_{\text{out}} : \mathbb{R}^{f^{(L)}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times f}$ maps the final features from the last time step to the λ -step prediction, completing the implementation of Ψ_ϕ .

C. Transformer-based Models

Transformers implement the prediction function Ψ_ϕ by using self-attention to model dependencies across sequences [5], [9]. The parameters $\phi = \{\mathbf{W}_{\text{emb}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{emb}}, \dots, \theta_{\text{out}}\}$ include embedding parameters $\mathbf{W}_{\text{emb}} \in \mathbb{R}^{f \times d_{\text{model}}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{\text{emb}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$. Given the input sequence $\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}$, we first project it into a d_{model} -dimensional space, where $d_{\text{model}} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the model's hidden dimension:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(0)} \triangleq \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t} \mathbf{W}_{\text{emb}} + \mathbf{b}_{\text{emb}} + \mathbf{P}. \quad (9)$$

Fixed positional encodings $\mathbf{P} \in \mathbb{R}^{\kappa \times d_{\text{model}}}$ are added to encode temporal order:

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{P}. \quad (10)$$

For each layer $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$, self-attention is computed as:

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) \mathbf{V}, \quad (11)$$

where $d_k \in \mathbb{N}$ is the attention dimension, and

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}_Q^{(l)}, \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}_K^{(l)}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{W}_V^{(l)}, \quad (14)$$

with $\mathbf{W}_Q^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_K^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_V^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}} \times d_k}$ being the query, key, and value projection matrices.

Each layer applies a feed-forward network:

$$\mathbf{H}^{(l)} = \sigma(\mathbf{H}^{(l-1)}\mathbf{W}_1^{(l)} + \mathbf{b}_1^{(l)})\mathbf{W}_2^{(l)} + \mathbf{b}_2^{(l)}, \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_1^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}} \times d_{\text{ff}}}$, $\mathbf{W}_2^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{ff}} \times d_{\text{model}}}$, $\mathbf{b}_1^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{ff}}}$, $\mathbf{b}_2^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}}$, $d_{\text{ff}} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the feed-forward dimension, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is an activation function.

The parameters ϕ consist of all learnable components:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi = \{ & \mathbf{W}_{\text{emb}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{emb}}, \\ & \{\mathbf{W}_Q^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_K^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_V^{(l)}, \\ & \mathbf{W}_1^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_2^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}_1^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}_2^{(l)}\}_{l=1}^L, \\ & \theta_{\text{out}} \} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

After L layers, the prediction is generated by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda} = f_{\text{out}}(\mathbf{H}_\kappa^{(L)}), \quad (17)$$

where $f_{\text{out}} : \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{model}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times f}$ maps the final representation to the λ -step prediction, completing the implementation of Ψ_ϕ .

D. Multi-Layer Perceptron-based Architectures

MLPs implement the prediction function Ψ_ϕ through direct non-linear mappings [10]. Given the input sequence $\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}$, we flatten it into a vector:

$$\mathbf{x} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{w}_{t-\kappa+1:t}) \in \mathbb{R}^{\kappa f}, \quad (18)$$

where $\text{vec}(\cdot)$ denotes vectorization by stacking the columns. For each layer $l \in \{1, \dots, L\}$, the hidden representation $\mathbf{h}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ is computed as:

$$\mathbf{h}^{(l)} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}^{(l)}\mathbf{h}^{(l-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}), \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{h}^{(0)} = \mathbf{x}$, $\mathbf{W}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l \times n_{l-1}}$, $\mathbf{b}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_l}$ with $n_0 = \kappa f$, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is an activation function. The parameters $\phi = \{\{\mathbf{W}^{(l)}, \mathbf{b}^{(l)}\}_{l=1}^L, \theta_{\text{out}}\}$ represent all learnable components. After L layers, the prediction is generated by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+1:t+\lambda} = f_{\text{out}}(\mathbf{h}^{(L)}), \quad (20)$$

where $f_{\text{out}} : \mathbb{R}^{n_L} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{\lambda \times f}$ maps the final hidden state to the λ -step prediction, completing the implementation of Ψ_ϕ .

E. Bayesian Optimization of Model Architecture for Workload Prediction

To optimize each machine learning model for the cloud-native workload prediction task, we employ Bayesian Optimization (BO) to efficiently tune the architecture and training configuration of Ψ_ϕ [11], [12]. Let Θ define the search space of valid hyperparameter configurations, where each configuration $\theta \in \Theta$ specifies the model architecture and training parameters. For a given configuration θ , we obtain the model parameters ϕ_θ through training on the workload trace \mathbf{W} .

Building on the workload prediction task defined in Section II, our objective is to find the ideal configuration (θ^*) that minimizes the expected validation MSE loss:

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}(\phi_\theta)]. \quad (21)$$

Fig. 1. Simplified Bayesian optimization example with one hyperparameter (λ): The surrogate model (blue line) approximates the true MSE function (dashed red) using observed errors (red dots). The blue shaded region indicates model uncertainty. The yellow star shows the next candidate to evaluate, while the concentric red circles mark the true optimum.

At each optimization iteration k , given previous evaluations $\mathcal{D}_k = \{(\theta_i, \mathcal{L}(\phi_{\theta_i}))\}_{i=1}^k$, a Gaussian Process fits a surrogate model through these observations, providing both an estimate of the expected error and uncertainty bounds. The next configuration is selected using the Expected Improvement (EI) acquisition function:

$$\alpha_k(\theta) = \mathbb{E} \left[\max(0, \min_{i \leq k} \mathcal{L}(\phi_{\theta_i}) - \mathcal{L}(\phi_{\theta})) \mid \mathcal{D}_k \right]. \quad (22)$$

Figure 1 provides a simplified illustration of the BO process for a single hyperparameter (prediction horizon λ), while in practice we optimize over a high-dimensional space including model architecture, training parameters, and feature dimensions f . **In this toy example**, the surrogate model (blue line) approximates the true MSE function (dashed red) based on observed errors (red dots), with uncertainty bounds shown in the blue shaded region. The star marks the next candidate ($\lambda = 5$) to evaluate, while the target symbol indicates the true optimum [8].

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We present a comprehensive evaluation of advanced time-series forecasting models applied to cloud-native workload prediction. Our assessment emphasizes prediction accuracy, computational efficiency, convergence behavior, and resource consumption, critical factors in cloud-native systems where rapid adaptability and resource optimization are essential.

A. Dataset

Following the workload representation in Section II, we evaluate our prediction framework on the Alibaba 2022 microservices trace dataset [13]. For pod `MS_11349`, we have $f = 2$ resource features, with workload vectors $\mathbf{w}_t = [w_t^{(1)}, w_t^{(2)}]^\top$ representing normalized CPU and memory utilization respectively. The trace contains $T = 18,720$ samples at 1-minute intervals, forming a workload matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{18720 \times 2}$. This dataset’s combination of daily patterns and demand spikes makes it suitable for evaluating prediction models with varying context windows κ and horizons λ .

B. Benchmarks

We compare five state-of-the-art models, each representing a distinct architecture: **FourierGNN** [3] combines GNNs with Fourier transforms to capture complex spatio-temporal dependencies; **ModernTCN** [4] employs temporal CNNs with advanced dilation to model long-range dependencies efficiently; **WGAN** [14] is a transformer-based model utilizing a generative adversarial approach; **Informer** [9] optimizes the Transformer architecture with efficient attention mechanisms; and **SparseTSF** [10] is a lightweight framework based on sparse MLPs, designed for fast inference and minimal resource consumption.

C. Experimental Settings

Experiments were conducted on a server with an NVIDIA A100 GPU (40 GB), 30 CPU cores, 200 GiB RAM, and 512 GiB SSD, running Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS. All models were implemented in Python using PyTorch. The hyperparameter search space Θ was explored using Bayesian optimization [8], [11], [12] with initial set \mathcal{D}_{n_0} of $n_0 = 20$ random configurations, followed by $n = 30$ iterations of guided search using the acquisition function α_k . The hyperparameter ranges defining Θ are summarized in Table I.

We assess model performance using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), computed as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} \|\mathbf{w}_{t+i} - \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+i}\|_1, \quad (23)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{\lambda} \|\mathbf{w}_{t+i} - \hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t+i}\|_2^2}, \quad (24)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_1$ and $\|\cdot\|_2$ denote the ℓ_1 and Euclidean norms in \mathbb{R}^f , respectively. We also consider inference time, convergence speed, number of parameters, and maximum memory usage—critical factors in cloud-native deployments where resource efficiency and rapid adaptability are essential.

D. Experimental Results

Our evaluation results are summarized in **Table II**. We analyze the performance of each model across the defined metrics.

1) *Prediction Accuracy (Fig. 2)*: Accurate workload prediction is essential in cloud-native scenarios for efficient resource allocation and maintaining Quality of Service. All models demonstrate strong predictive capabilities, but key differences emerge. **ModernTCN** attains the best performance for memory prediction (RMSE: 3.58×10^{-4}), indicating its effectiveness in modeling temporal patterns. **SparseTSF** achieves the lowest RMSE and MAE for CPU prediction (RMSE: 2.85×10^{-3}), closely followed by **ModernTCN** and **Informer**. As detailed in Section III-A, **FourierGNN**’s message passing and graph

TABLE I
HYPERPARAMETER RANGES FOR BAYESIAN OPTIMIZATION

Hyperparameter	FourierGNN	ModernTCN	WGAN	Informer	SparseTSF
Seq. len. (L_s)	48-256	48-336	12-48	24-256	48-128
Pred. len. (L_p)	12-96	12-96	1-24	12-64	12-24
Batch size (B)	16-128	32-512	16-128	16-64	128-512
Learn. rate (η)	1e-4 - 1e-2	1e-4 - 1e-2	-	-	1e-3 - 3e-2
Embed size (d_m)	32-256	32-512	16-128	64-512	64-512
Num. heads (N_h)	-	1-8	2-8	4-16	4-8
Enc. layers (L_e)	-	1-4	1-4	1-4	1-3
Dec. layers (L_d)	-	-	1-4	1-3	-
Dropout (p_d)	0-0.5	0-0.5	0-0.5	0.15-0.4	0.1-0.4
FF dim. (d_f)	-	-	-	128-1024	64-512
Hidden (d_h)	64-512	-	-	-	-
Period (L_{per})	-	-	-	-	4-60
Label (L_{label})	-	-	-	32-64	-
Weight decay (λ_w)	-	-	1e-6 - 1e-2	-	-
Lambda GP (λ_{GP})	-	-	1-20	-	-
Patience (p)	10	10	10	10	10

TABLE II
COMPREHENSIVE PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF WORKLOAD PREDICTION MODELS (RED INDICATES BEST PERFORMANCE, ORANGE INDICATES SECOND-BEST)

Model	Memory		CPU		Inference Time (ms)	Convergence (epochs)	Time/Epoch (s)	# Parameters (number)	Max Memory Usage (bytes)
	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE					
ModernTCN	3.58e-04	2.75e-04	2.88e-03	2.26e-03	7.15e-03	10	3.81	247,091	988,364
FGNN	8.54e-03	8.51e-03	6.00e-03	5.18e-03	3.47e-02	10	7.71	330,318	1,321,272
Informer	2.35e-03	2.22e-03	2.95e-03	2.32e-03	5.21e-01	10	22.76	2,429,278	9,717,112
SparseTSF	3.99e-04	2.95e-04	2.85e-03	2.25e-03	1.84e-03	10	1.23	35	140
WGAN	2.13e-03	1.79e-03	4.46e-03	3.61e-03	3.23e+00	43	2.59	2,889,815	11,559,260

Fig. 2. Predicted vs. true values for memory (top) and CPU (bottom) utilization. Lightgrey solid lines represent true values; dashed lines show model predictions.

structure smooth out sudden CPU spikes, while compression into $\mathbf{h}_\kappa^{(L)}$ loses critical temporal dynamics, leading to lower prediction accuracy.

2) *Inference Time (Fig. 3)*: Low inference latency is critical for real-time decision-making in cloud-native environments. **SparseTSF** demonstrates the fastest infer-

Fig. 3. Inference times for various models on workload prediction tasks.

ence time (1.84 μ s), making it highly suitable for edge deployments with latency constraints. **ModernTCN** and **FourierGNN** also exhibit low inference times, benefiting from efficient architectures. In contrast, **Informer** and **WGAN** have significantly higher inference times due to their complex attention mechanisms, which may introduce unacceptable delays in scenarios requiring rapid scaling decisions.

3) *Convergence Behavior (Fig. 4)*: The dynamic nature of traffic in cloud-native environments can cause model performance to degrade over time, necessitating online retraining for accurate predictions. This requires models to have short convergence times to support efficient orchestration decisions. Among the evaluated approaches, **SparseTSF** and **ModernTCN** achieve rapid convergence within 10 epochs, enabling quick adaptation to new traffic patterns. While **Informer** also converges quickly, it incurs higher computational costs per epoch. In contrast, **WGAN**'s adversarial training process leads to longer

Fig. 4. Normalized MSE training loss convergence across models.

Fig. 5. Logarithmic comparison of model complexity: Number of parameters and maximum memory usage.

convergence times and higher training variability, making it less suitable for scenarios requiring consistent and rapid model updates.

4) *Model Complexity and Size (Fig. 5)*: Resource efficiency is critical in cloud-native deployments, particularly at the edge. **SparseTSF** stands out with only 35 parameters and minimal memory usage (140 bytes), ideal for resource-constrained devices. **ModernTCN** and **FourierGNN** offer a balance between complexity and performance, suitable for environments with moderate resources. **Informer** and **WGAN**, with millions of parameters and higher memory requirements, are more appropriate for powerful edge nodes or cloud servers. This significant variation underscores the importance of matching model complexity to deployment environments, balancing accuracy, latency, and resource consumption.

5) *Discussion*: Our results highlight key trade-offs in cloud workload prediction. On the periodic Alibaba traces (Fig. 2), **SparseTSF** excels by leveraging its strength in modeling cyclic patterns [10], with Bayesian optimization (Section III-E) effectively tuning its parameters to the strong periodicity. However, this performance may not generalize to less predictable workloads. **ModernTCN**, despite its higher resource requirements, offers better architectural support for non-periodic patterns whilst having better performance, a trade-off that warrants future investigation. **FourierGNN** struggles with rapid temporal dynamics, while **Informer** and **WGAN**'s computational demands limit their edge deployment.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have fine-tuned different time-series models for workload prediction in cloud-edge environments using Bayesian optimization. **SparseTSF** consistently outperformed other models, delivering the best balance of accuracy, inference speed, and resource efficiency, making it suitable for both edge and cloud scenarios. Our findings highlight the importance of optimizing model architectures to meet the diverse demands of cloud-edge systems, offering concrete guidance for enhancing workload prediction and resource management in dynamic environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is supported by the VERGE project (SNS-JU-101096034) under Horizon Europe and the AVANZANDO-5G-GEMELOS DIGITALES project (TSI-063000-2021-112/113/114) under UNICO-5G-RPTR.

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